

Smart Medication system Using IoT

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Abstract— In order to ensure that patients take their medications at the correct times, this research suggests a new approach: providing them with the necessary information automatically. Nowadays, most patients experience emotional stress, which might cause them to forget to take their medications as prescribed. Therefore, it may cause the recovery time from the disorders to be longer. It may be a serious issue when elderly individuals swallow their pills too quickly, leading to an erroneous dose level. And hence, it is critical for the patient to take their medication exactly as prescribed, at the exact same time each day. An innovative Smart Medication Dispenser (SMD) technology is suggested as a solution to these issues. To remind patients to take their medication at the prescribed times, this system makes use of a 4x4 matrix keypad, microcontroller, LCD display, real-time clock (RTC) module, global system for mobile communications (GSM) module, and alarm system. The elderly, and particularly the uneducated, might benefit from this affordable and portable SMD system.

Key Words— Arduino Uno, AMR, ANN, LCDRFID, and RTC.

I. INTRODUCTION

People nowadays are so busy that they often forget to take their medications as directed. The elderly are at risk of being unnecessarily hospitalised because of this. Therefore, the tablets should be dispensed at predetermined intervals by means of a system or device [1]. From the very beginning of medicine's pill form, there has been a need for a mechanism that could precisely substitute a person for the task of pill delivery. To this day, no

automated pill dispenser has been able to take the role of humans in deciding who should get pills, when they should get them, and in what quantities. Taking medicines at home comes with its own share of complications, such as the possibility of pill theft, forgetfulness, or accidental overdosing. We devised a solution based on these users' fundamental requirements, which involves a basic microcontroller for pill dispensing management and a proximity sensor for reading and allowing access to only valid keys [4]. The potential uses, functions, and accessibility of this pill dispenser to a wide range of individuals are almost limitless. The addition of a buzzer to this pill dispenser makes it dual-purpose: it reminds you to take your medicines at the prescribed times and also alerts others when you forget to take them. Some of the most fundamental tasks that an accessed controlled pill dispenser might do are listed below.

Hospitals Domestic

Automated pill dispensers may streamline the process of dosing pills for both small and big hospitals. By using a pill dispenser, medical professionals may greatly decrease the time spent on preparation and "rounds," allowing them to devote more attention to patients requiring urgent medical care. A basic database may also be used to notify medical practitioners about who and when medication is delivered.

A. Domestic

Another potential market for automated pill dispensers is the growing number of people

who take multivitamins and other nutritional supplements on a regular basis, either with meals or at the same time. A buzzer may serve as a reminder for when the supplements need to be taken, and a keychain key can start the pill distribution process for the user's specific eating regimen. Some of the most fundamental functions that an accessed controlled pill dispenser could perform include controlling who can access sensitive medications (e.g., those for children or teenagers), locking the dispenser so that only the owner with the key on their keychain can remove the pills, and activating the dispenser at specific times of day.

People in their twilight years Prepare your final version, including figures and tables, in two-column style and submit it when your article has been approved.
II. History of Methods

A plethora of tools and software programmes have emerged in recent years to facilitate the administration of complex drugs, thanks to advancements in electronic communication networks. Automatic medicine dispensers and alarm clocks are two of the most practical options. Someone may be reminded to go to their pillbox on a daily, weekly, or monthly basis and take their prescription on time using an alarm watch that has an audible or vibrating sound. Alarm watches allow users to set many alarms throughout the day, making them ideal for accommodating irregular medication regimens. These watches are difficult to programme, and unclear instructions may quickly annoy elderly people. An Android-based medication reminder system is another viable alternative to the complicated drug reminder dilemma. An ANN-based OCR-based Android-based Medication Reminder System [2]. This approach makes use of an Android-based app that patients may utilise. The user will be reminded to take their medication correctly by this app. When it's time, by automatically setting reminders on the phone. In accordance with the prescription, the programme will automatically schedule these reminders. Patients will be reminded to

correctly take their medication by this reminder. The only demographic this strategy will work for is young people on Android phones. However, it is very challenging to use and comprehend for elderly individuals who are illiterate. The system's gadget is expensive, and developing an app for Android is a painstaking process. An alarm system, numerous pill containers, a motor controller, an LED display, an alphanumeric keyboard, and a microcontroller interface make up this automatic medication dispenser design. With some automation, it functions as a gadget [8]. To make it easier for the user to specify when to disperse, that's the standard operating method.

more than one medication at the prescribed times. At this point, the user must push a button in order to retrieve the pill container and reset the alarm. The technique makes use of a motor controller. This means you'll need an extra 12V to power the motor, and it's only going to work with a select few medications. It is not a portable equipment, and there are more risks of mishandling it. As far as costs go, it's not cheap. People Who Live Alone Can Benefit from an Intelligent Pill Dispenser. The SMD is a lockable, automated medicine dispenser that may dispense up to six times daily. The SMD was created so that the carer may rest easy knowing that their patient is taking the correct medicine at the appropriate time. Patients are reminded to take their medication via a long-lasting alert when this SMD goes off. When a patient forgets to take their medication or takes too much, an alarm will go off for 15 minutes to alert a carer. It may send a message, email, or phone call to the carer from afar if the patient forgets to take their medication. The current setup may notify the carer by email or text message when it is time to restock medication. Protect your medicine with the SMD lockable pill dispenser. In order to get the right dose, it includes a revolving disc with many sections where the pills are divided. Upon activation of the alarm, the device's disc will revolve to indicate the subsequent dose. To get the pills into their hands, the patient inverts the gadget [2]. When a person doesn't take their

medication, the box shifts to a different location. These help the user avoid taking the erroneous dosage when it's time for their next medication. Because of its small size and lightweight design, SMD is ideal for those who are always on the go. Thanks to its built-in scale, this device offers an automated operation that makes medicine administration a breeze.

II. METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

The article includes information on the smart medicine dispenser's (SMD) design. After gathering all of the necessary criteria to create this gadget, careful attention is given to the design process. At last, a method for creating an automated medication dispenser is proposed. The caretaker may dependably deliver medicines to patients without being physically there every time thanks to the programmable automated medicine dispenser. An ergonomically built interface with an alphanumeric keypad and LCD display enables the carer to pre-program the SMD to set up to 21 medication doses. It is possible to set the SMD to repeat the same cycle for a month in advance. The number of tablets or capsules is alerted to load the medication when it drops below a user-configurable threshold. Computer parts
Initial Plan: A. Energy Source

The SMD controller will get the power it needs from the power supply circuit. Apart than that, the motor requires 12V. The motor controller design mostly dictates the current needs, which are 5 VDC for the motor and microcontroller and 100mA for the microcontroller. In order to prevent the loss of user input choices and time keeping capabilities, it is possible that the power supply will need a battery backup.

The Keyboard and Screen
The input keypad is a conventional 16-key alphabetic keypad. The user is able to code the machine with its help [4]. The user may see the time set or reset action on the alpha numeric display unit. It shows the user what's within the container graphically. When necessary, the same device may be utilised to provide the warning.

A. Speaker

The Speaker is provided to give a beep sound to warn the patient regarding the time to take the tablet. The same speaker is also use to call the name of the patient which provides the information regarding the updating the pills/capsules into the container. This facility helps the blind to interact with SMD.

B. Microcontroller

The microcontroller is the main part of the SMD. It is responsible for performing all the functions and commands of the medicine box. The microcontroller is selected to meet the required functionality of the SMD without wasting money on unneeded features. The basic requirements of the microcontroller are a few Input output ports to interface the keyboard, display unit, motor, and speaker. Interrupts are used to enable the user to interact with the system for programming. When the user presses the command key, it enables the user to program the timing and set the required pills to be available in the output poach. The command key also allows the user to program the number of minimum pills/capsules that must be made available before a warning signal is provided. The Microcontroller is so chosen that the system does not require additional external peripheral chips and memory. The memory requirement is 2K of READ Only memory and 8K of Read writes memory.

E. Pill Container and Dispenser

The pill/capsule container design will have 30 slots with 21 available for medications. The 21 slots will be labeled so that the caregiver can ensure setting the alarm for the correct slot. Additionally, the pill container will incorporate interlock sensors to protect the caregiver and user from harm. Finally the sensors [4] will provide input to the microcontroller for determining access doors status, medication slot positioning and time feedback of the patient accessing the medications.

F. Alarm Module

The alarm module will provide an audible alarm tone . This module is designed to send a pattern of audible sounds through the speaker till the patient responds by pressing the button to access the pouch for the pills/capsules. An LED is also provided to blink during the alarm process. A visual display string is provided for the user to read the instruction. A second alarm is provided to prompt the caretaker to load the pills/capsules when the number of pills/capsules in the storage unit falls

below the threshold value. The number of pills/capsules threshold value is also programmable [7]. This alarm does not provide audio but gives a warning by blinking.

G. Motor Controller

All motors have a control device called a motor controller to start and stop the motor called a motor controller. It is the actual device that energizes and de-energizes the circuit of the motor so that it can start or stop. The design of the motor controller will be determined by the current requirement of the stepper motor selected. The motor controller takes logic inputs from the microcontroller and supply enough current to the stepper motor to meet maximum torque requirements.

H. LED

The Light emitting diode display will be a simple red light; it provides information such as power on, flashing as he speaker beeps to have the attention of the user and emergency indication[7]. It also provides pre-selected precautions to the patient concerning the medications being currently dispensed.

VI. RESULT

The display units of the systems for displaying various parameters and messages to the user. the GSM module for intimation for missing the dosage by the patient. Finally gives the complete system for the proposed Smart Medication

The MAX232 device is a dual driver/receiver that includes a capacitive voltage generator to supply EIA-232 voltage levels from a single 5-V supply. Each receiver converts EIA-232 input to 5-V TTL/CMOS levels. The modem can either be connected to PC serial port directly or to any microcontroller. It can be used to send and receive SMS or make/receive voice calls. It can also be used in GPRS mode to connect to internet and do many applications for data logging and control.

Fig -2: Display the project name

Dispenser

The power supply circuit will provide 5v for microcontroller and 12v for motor. Controller provides serial clock and serial data to RTC. The DS1307 Serial Real-Time Clock is a low-power; full binary-coded decimal (BCD) clock/calendar plus 56 bytes of NV SRAM. Address and data are transferred serially via a 2-wire, bi-directional bus. The clock/calendar provides seconds, minutes, hours, day, date, month, and year information. Serial data and clock information to D7. Then this information displayed on LCD. The L293 and L293D are quadruple high-current half-H drivers. The L293 is designed to provide bidirectional drive currents of up to 1 A at voltages from 4.5 V to 36 V. The L293D is designed to provide bidirectional drive currents of up to 600-mA at voltages from 4.5 V to 36 V.

VII. CONCLUSION

For elderly patients, who may have trouble remembering to take their medication or who may have trouble reading the names of their medications, the suggested method is a great aid. A total of four times a day, it may sound an alert. If the patient continues to disregard the alert and does not take their medication as prescribed, the SMD system will contact the specified number stored in its memory. Modifying the frequency of medication administration according to need is within the realm of possibility in programming.

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